

Research Article

Studies on Phytochemical Analysis of Leaf & Clove Extract of *Allium Sativum*

G. R. Katkar*¹, R. S. Dubal²

¹Department of Zoology, Rayat Institute of Research and Development, Satara 415001 (MS) India.

²Department of Zoology Krantiagrani Dr. G. D. Babu Lad Mahavidyalaya, Kundal Sangli 416309 (MS) India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 21 Mar. 2025

Keywords:

Allium sativum, Soxhlet apparatus, Phytochemicals, Secondary Metabolites.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15062607

ABSTRACT

The secondary metabolites present in medicinal plants are crucial for curing diseases and are also used as essential raw materials for the production of conventional and modern medicines. Garlic (*Allium sativum*, L.) is a bulbous annual flowering plant belonging to the family Liliaceae (Juss. 1789). Aqueous, Alcohol and Acetone extracts of garlic leaves and cloves were prepared using a Soxhlet apparatus. Phytochemical assays were carried out as per the standard protocol for the screening of phytochemical compounds. The phytochemical screening of aqueous, alcohol, and acetone extract showed the presence of glycosides, terpenoids flavonoids, phenols, carbohydrates, proteins, alkaloids, tannins, and flavanol. The alcoholic extract of cloves and leaves exhibited less compounds compared to Aqueous and Acetonic extracts. A review of literature suggests that components present in the extract are medically important and are used as antioxidant, radioprotective, antilipemic, antibiotic, antihypertensive, antiviral, antimicrobial, anticancer, immunomodulatory, anti-mutagenic, and anti-tumor effects.

INTRODUCTION

A. sativum (Garlic) is bulbous plant with hermaphrodite flowers with white petals possesses a shallow adventitious root system. Its leaves are flat and resemble have circular leaves. The leaves resemble grass and are long. There are many seeds in the fruit. Its flowers have four white petals each. In April, garlic blossoms¹. The bioactive

phytochemical components present in some plant definitely produce physiological effects on human body^{2,3}. Secondary metabolites found in medicinal plants are crucial in controlling several ailments and serve as vital raw materials for the production of both traditional and contemporary medicines⁴. By using phytochemical and physicochemical methods essential oils of the *Allium sativum* and

*Corresponding Author: G. R. Katkar

Address: Department of Zoology, Rayat Institute of Research and Development, Satara 415001 (MS) India.

Email : grkatkar2707@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Allium cepa were characterized⁵. More than 500 species of the *Allium* Genus bear various taste and have similar biochemical, phytochemical, and nutraceutical Properties⁶. The Phytochemical constituents of *A. sativum* has anticancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antithrombotic, hypocholesterolemic, hypoglycemic, and hypotensive properties and are used to prevent and treat a variety of illnesses, including cold and flu symptoms. This is achieved through immune enhancement. It also serves as a treatment for hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidemia, atherosclerosis, and thrombosis. It also exerts antiplatelet activity, which prevents blood clots, stroke, and gastrointestinal neoplasia⁷. Researchers observed phytochemicals in garlic and showed various bioactive components are Glycosides, Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Phenols, Terpenoids, Saponins, Carbohydrates, Proteins, Starch, Tannins, Flavanol and Anthocynin compounds⁸. Many vitamins, minerals, and trace elements can be found in fresh

garlic, however most are present in very little amounts. Sulfur concentration is greater in garlic than in any other *Allium* species. Due to their detectable levels, germanium and selenium are two traces of the element proposed to show the anti-tumor activities of the herb⁹. The use of medicinal plants in disease management is flourishing because they are economical, environmentally safe, and have few negative effects. Herbs have long been utilized in both human and veterinary medicine.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS:

2.1 Collection and Authentication of plant:

The (Garlic) *A. sativum* plant collected from a farm in Satara District, Maharashtra, India. The identification and authentication of plant was done at Department of Botany, Yashwantrao Chavan Institute of Science, Satara. (See fig.1 and Fig.2).

Fig. 1. Leaves of *A. sativum*

Fig. 2. Cloves of *A. sativum*

2.2 Preparation of Extract carried out by Soxhlet method.

The plants cloves and leaves were removed, cleaned, and air-dried under a canopy at room temperature for a few days. The shade dried leaves and cloves are grinded into a fine powder and stored in glass vials at room temperature. Using

Soxhlet apparatus 20 gm of leaves and cloves powder in 200 ml of each extracted in required solvents Aqueous, Alcohol and Acetone¹⁰. Then plant extracts were concentrated using a high-speed evaporator and preserved in the refrigerator and used for phytochemical analysis screening¹¹.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preliminary phytochemical analysis of Aqueous, Alcohol and Acetone Cloves and Leaves extracts of *Allium sativum* were mentioned in Table :1

Table :1 Preliminary Phytochemical analysis of extracts of *Allium sativum* (Garlic) as follows:

Chemical Constituents	Test	Cloves extracts of <i>Allium sativum</i> (Garlic)			Leaves extracts of <i>Allium sativum</i> (Garlic)		
		Aqueous	Alcohol	Acetone	Aqueous	Alcohol	Acetone
Glycosides	Raymond's	-	-	+	-	-	-
	Keller killiani	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Legal's	+	+	-	+	-	+
Alkaloids	Wagner's	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Hager's	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Mayer's	-	-	+	-	-	-
Flavonoids	Lead acetate solution	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Shinoda	+	-	-	+	+	-
	Ferric chloride	+	-	-	+	+	+
	Zinc-Hydrochlori acid-reduction	+	-	-	+	+	-
	Alkaline reagent	-	+	+	-	+	+
Steroids	Chloroform	+	-	+	+	+	+
	Salkowski	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Sulphur	-	-	-	-	-	-
Phenols	Fec13	+	+	-	+	+	+
Terpenoids	Salkowaski	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Liebermann Burchard	+	-	+	+	+	+
	Biuret	-	+	+	-	+	+
	Ninhydrin	-	-	-	-	-	-
Saponins	Foam	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Raymond's	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carbohydrates	Molisch's	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Benedict's	-	-	+	-	-	-
	Leagal's	-	-	-	+	-	+
Proteins	Xanthoproteic	-	-	+	-	-	+
	Millon's	-	-	-	-	+	+
	Ninhydrin	-	-	-	-	-	-
Starch	Starch Reagent	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tannins	Gelatin	-	-	+	-	-	-
	NaoH	-	-	-	-	+	+
Flavanol	Lead acetate solution	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Shinoda	+	-	-	+	+	-
	Ferric chloride	+	+	-	+	+	-
	Alkaline reagent	-	-	+	-	+	+
	Zinc-Hydrochloric acid-reduction	+	-	-	+	+	-
Anthocynin	HCL	-	-	-	-	-	-

+ Present - Absent

Fig. 3 PCA: Phytochemical analysis of Aqueous, Alcohol, and Acetone Cloves and Leaves extracts of *Allium sativum* (Garlic).

A principal component analysis (PCA) helps to reduce data dimensionality and easily visualize complex data. Further, it demonstrates how to characterize under the consideration related to one another and how that related to content separation during phytochemical analysis. Five of the main components (PCs) in this investigation had eigenvalues greater than one, the variance seen among two plant parts and different three type solvent under 13 phytochemical parameter. The distribution of the two plant parts sample under study is depicted in the biplot (Fig.3) of the first two PCs, where PCs PC1 and PC2 have reported 74.20% and 16.75% variance of the original data, respectively. PC1 and PC2's combined percentage was 90.95%. Assessment of parameter loading was done to look into PC factors¹². Preliminary Phytochemical investigation of Aqueous cloves extract of *Allium sativum* showed the presence of Glycosides, Flavonoids, Steroids, Phenols, Carbohydrates and Flavanol while in Alcoholic cloves extract of *A. sativum* showed the presence of Glycosides, Flavonoids, Steroids, Phenols, Terpenoids, Carbohydrates and Flavanol and

Phytochemical analysis of Acetonic cloves extract of *A. sativum* showed the presence of Glycosides, Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Terpenoids, Carbohydrates, Proteins, Tannins and Flavanol. Among these three solvents Acetonic extract showed the presence of more compounds as compared to Aqueous and Alcoholic extract. Preliminary phytochemical analysis of aqueous leaves extract of *A. sativum* indicates the presence of Glycosides, Flavonoids, Steroids, Phenols, Terpenoids, Carbohydrates, Flavanol while Alcoholic leaves extract of *A. sativum* showed the presence of Glycosides, Flavonoids, Steroids, Phenols, Terpenoids, carbohydrates, Proteins, Tannins and Flavanol and Phytochemical analysis of acetonic leaves extract of *A. sativum* showed the presence of Glycosides, Flavonoids, Steroids, Phenols, Terpenoids, carbohydrates, Proteins, Tannins and Flavanol. Among these three solvents alcoholic and acetonic extract showed the presence of more compounds as compared to aqueous extract in leaves. From the above result it has been observed that Preliminary phytochemical evaluation of Aqueous, Alcoholic

and Acetonic cloves and leaves extract of *A. sativum* constitute Glycosides, Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Terpenoids, Carbohydrates, Proteins, Tannins and Flavanol. A similar result were also observed by⁷. Hexane, Ethyl acetate, Methanol and Aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* contains Alkaloids, phenolics, Flavonoids, Steroids, glycosides and saponins, carbohydrates, terpenoids and tannins. Similar observations were also showed by¹³. Aqueous and Ethanol extract of *A. sativum* and *C. longa* consists of Saponins, alkaloids, tannin, Flavonoids, glycosides, lipids, ketones and phlobutanin. Various solvent extracts of *A. sativum* and *A. cepa* contains glycosides, alkaloids, Saponins, steroids, Flavonoids, phenols, tannins and Terpenoids⁸. Similar phytochemical observations were also noted by¹⁴. that Aqueous and Methanol extract of *A. sativum* possess anthraquinones, Saponins, triterpenes, Flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids and glycosides. Similar findings of phytochemical analysis of water, Ethanol and Acetone extracts of *Allium sativum* contains Reducing sugar, lipids, flavonoids, ketones, alkaloids, steroids and triterpenes¹⁵.

4. CONCLUSION:

From the above study it has been concluded that the constituents present in extracts of *A. sativum* are medically important and are used as Antioxidant, Radioprotective, Antilipemic, Antihypertensive, Antiviral, Antimicrobial, Anticancerous, Immunomodulatory, Anti-mutagenic effects and Anti- tumor. The research in this line is in progress in our laboratory.

5. Conflict Of Interest:

No other researchers have shown a conflict of-interest concern with our research.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The authors are thankful to Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Research and Training Institute (MAHAJYOTI) for providing a fellowship to Geeta Ramesh Katkar under MJPRF-2022. The authors are also thankful to the Director, Principal Dr. B. T. Jadhav Rayat Institute of Research and Development, Satara for providing facilities to conduct the present research.

REFERENCES

1. Okigbo RN, Ezebo RO, Okoli SI. Phytochemical analysis of *Xylopiya aethiopia* (Dun), *Citrus limon* (L.) and *Allium sativum* (L.) extracts and their effect on selected human pathogens. *Adv Med Plant Res.* 2020;8:35-42.
2. Dhawale PG. Phytochemical Analysis of Some Medicinal Plants from Yavatmal District (Ms) India. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science.* 2013;2(1):65-6.
3. Yadav RN, Agarwala M. Phytochemical analysis of some medicinal plants. *Journal of phytology.* 2011 Dec 14;3(12).
4. Singh V, Kumar R. Study of phytochemical analysis and antioxidant activity of *Allium sativum* of Bundelkhand region. *International Journal of Life-Sciences Scientific Research.* 2017 Nov;3(6):1451-8.
5. Boukeria S, Kadi K, Kalleb R, Benbott A, Bendjedou D, Yahia A. Phytochemical and physicochemical characterization of *Allium sativum* L. and *Allium cepa* L. Essential oils. *J. Mater. Environ. Sci.* 2016;7(7):2362-8.
6. Dalhat MH, Adefolake FA, Musa M. Nutritional composition and phytochemical analysis of aqueous extract of *Allium cepa* (onion) and *Allium sativum* (garlic). *Asian Food Sci. J.* 2018;3(4):1-9.
7. Divya BJ, Suman B, Venkataswamy M, Thyagaraju K. A study on phytochemicals, functional groups and mineral composition of *Allium sativum* (garlic) cloves. *Int J Curr Pharm Res.* 2017 May;9(3):42-5.

8. Efiog EE, Akumba LP, Chukwu EC, Olusesan AI, Obochi G. Comparative qualitative phytochemical analysis of oil, juice and dry forms of garlic (*Allium sativum*) and different varieties of onions (*Allium cepa*) consumed in Makurdi metropolis. *International Journal of Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*. 2020 Jan 31;12(1):9-16.
9. Mikail HG. Phytochemical screening, elemental analysis and acute toxicity of aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* L. bulbs in experimental rabbits. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*. 2010 Feb 18;4(4):322-6.
10. Gopalsatheeskumar K. Significant role of soxhlet extraction process in phytochemical research. *Mintage Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Sciences*. 2018;7(1):43-7.
11. Khandelwal K. *Practical pharmacognosy*. Pragati Books Pvt. Ltd.; 2008 Sep 7.
12. Alam MS, Tester M, Fiene G, Mousa MA. Early growth stage characterization and the biochemical responses for salinity stress in tomato. *Plants*. 2021 Apr 7;10(4):712.
13. Nazir I, Chauhan RS. Qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Allium sativum* (Garlic) and *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric). *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud*. 2019;7(1):545-7.
14. Garba I, Umar AI, Abdulrahman AB, Tijjani MB, Aliyu MS, Zango UU, Muhammad A. Phytochemical and antibacterial properties of garlic extracts. *Bayero Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*. 2013;6(2):45-8.
15. Olusanmi MJ, Amadi JE. Studies on the antimicrobial properties and phytochemical screening of garlic (*Allium sativum*) extracts. *Ethnobotanical leaflets*. 2010;2009(9):10

HOW TO CITE: G. R. Katkar*, R. S. Dubal, Studies on Phytochemical Analysis of Leaf & Clove Extract of *Allium Sativum*, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 3, 2028-2033. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15062607>